

TEACHING ENGLISH LANGUAGE TO YOUNG LEARNERS BY USING INTERACTIVE GAMES

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ABSTRACT: The article deals with a great difference of methods of educating foreign languages to young generations namely pupils. Each teaching method is mainly based on a particular vision of comprehension the language or the learning process, frequently using specific techniques and materials used in a set sequence.

KEYWORDS: method, specific techniques, games, communication, student, teacher, pupil, interactive, vocabulary, form of training. **INTRODUCTION:** The problem arising in this contemporary education society is that learning today has changed and its process somehow differs from that in the past. So where does the difference lie? In the earlier years, the main focus of education is on the acquisition of the basic skills as well as content knowledge ranging from reading, writing, calculating, history and science. On the contrary, what accounts for a success in learning or education today is the ability to use high order skills including the ability to think through, to solve complex problems, and to interact critically through language. This, somehow, implies that one is in need of mastering how to use language to communicate his or her own thought effectively. On the other hand, one true fact about language learning is that it is believed to be a difficult task that most of the time will trigger frustration out of a learner. The learner, at every moment, is required to accumulate and maintain constant effort in order to understand and produce the target language. In these recent years, language researchers, as well as language specialists, have managed to change their focus from just developing individual linguistic skills to the use of language to achieve the speakers' objectives instead, which has been recognized as communicative competence. This area of focus has brought about the scenario in which language instructors or teachers devote great effort to seek any task-oriented activities that will engage learners in creative language use. With a deliberate effort, it has been noticed that games, which are regarded as task-based, do serve as effective communicative activities that go beyond the production of correct speech¹ According to Roth, playing is a child's natural way of learning. Since birth, play—constructive play—constitutes the fundamental aspects of children's intellectual, emotional, social, and physical development (NIU). By exposing to the learning environment in which there is

an existence of constructive play, children are confirmed to expand their intelligence, for instance, their knowledge and understanding of the world around them (NIU). In this sense, play thereupon helps prepare children for their academic learning once they begin their school years and even at each step along the academic journey. However, the most common misconception about learning is that it is supposed to be serious, intense, and, no doubt, solemn in nature. If a person, in his or her learning environment, is experiencing fun or is exposed to hilarity and laughter, it is assumed that he or she is not really learning. Despite this fact, one needs to accept that it is still possible to learn as well as enjoy oneself at the same time. When it comes down to learning environment of children, it is almost impossible to separate playing from learning. This is due to an undeniable fact that children love to play, and most importantly, plays happen to mirror what is important in their lives. Conclusively, play is accepted to be a preparation for children towards the prospective rewarding adult lives (NIU). 2 Based on the above definitions of and opinions about games from different writers, an importance of games has highly been valued in teaching. This further emphasizes that when games are being used in class, they do not only help students to learn more effectively but also to have fun at the same time. Consequently, language instructors, specifically teachers, have started to acknowledge that, in terms of teaching techniques, games will serve not only as an ‘amusing activity’, but also as a technique to carry out tasks to learners in an amusing kind of way as well. However, even many language instructors seems to be immensely enthusiastic in using games as educational tools, they normally still consider games as mere time-fillers—a break from the monotony drilling—or frivolous activities. The reason behind this, according to Silvers, should be the perception of those teachers who overlook the fact that within a relaxed atmosphere, real learning does take place; thus, students tend to use the language they have been given instruction to and have practiced earlier. In spite of all the facts, in the interest of revealing the benefits of using games for language learning, reported the nine main beneficial aspects including:

1. Games are learner-centered (the student is always in focus).

2. Games promote communicative competence.

3. Games create meaningful context for language use.

4. Games increase learning motivation. 5. Games reduce learning anxiety. 6. Games integrate linguistic skills. 7. Games encourage creativity and spontaneous usage of the language. 8. Games construct a cooperative usage of the language. 9. Games foster the participatory attitudes of the students.

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